

Group

	0	1	2	3	4	5, ..., K		
A	0	0	5	10	15	20	25	...
σ_A	3	10	40	70	100	130	160	...
B	2	1	6	11	16	21	26	...
σ_B	5	16	46	76	106	136	166	...
C	4	2	7	12	17	22	27	...
σ_C	7	22	52	82	112	142	172	...
D	6	3	8	13	18	23	28	...
σ_D	89	28	58	88	118	148	178	...
E	8	4	9	14	19	24	29	...
σ_E	1	4	34	64	94	124	154	...

there exist + parity / color